

COMPARISON OF SINGLE FIBER FRAGMENTATION AND MICRO-INDENTATION TESTS FOR COMPOSITE INTERFACIAL SHEAR STRENGTH MEASUREMENT

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ABSTRACT

The adhesion of the preceramic fiber coatings heat treated in N₂ at selected temperatures (200°C increments to 1000°C) was evaluated. Single fiber fragmentation and microindentation tests were applied to derive the interfacial shear strengths. Significant discrepancy was found in the interfacial shear strength values obtained from these two methods, especially for fiber coatings treated at high temperatures. Nonlinear finite element analyses were performed to study the test mechanics. It was found that these two tests are measuring different interfacial properties. While the microindentation test is an interfacial shear strength test, the single fiber fragmentation test should be regarded as interfacial toughness test.

INTRODUCTION

It is well recognized that the interfacial/phasal properties between polymer matrix and reinforcing fiber play a key role in determining the ultimate mechanical properties of a composite material. In recent years, researchers have been engineering the interphase to satisfy specific composite performance requirements [1-6]. For example, while a rubber coating was applied to a fiber to increase the composite fracture toughness [6], a ceramic coating was used to enhance the fiber oxidation resistance and fiber-matrix adhesion [2,3]. For all applications, the effects of the processing variables, such as the interphase properties, thickness, in addition to the encompassing matrix properties, on the interfacial shear strength needs to be well understood in order to optimize the composite performance.

In the last three decades, several micro tests have been developed to characterize the fiber/matrix interfacial properties [7]. Among all, the single fiber fragmentation test is the most frequently used technique due to its simplicity. For single fiber fragmentation test, a continuous single fiber is embedded in the matrix and casted into a dog-bone coupon. The coupon is then subjected to a tensile load. Since the failure strain of the matrix is much higher than that of the fiber, the fiber will fracture into small segments within the matrix as the applied load increases. After fiber fracture occurs, axial stresses are induced in the broken fibers by interfacial shear stress. The fibers will fracture again as higher tensile loads are applied. The fracture process continues until all remaining fiber lengths become so short that the interfacial shear stress can no longer build up enough tensile stresses to cause any further failures with increasing strains. This final fragmentation length of the fiber is referred to as the critical length l_c . If the fiber and matrix are perfectly bonded and the matrix material is perfectly plastic, the interfacial shear strength τ can then be calculated by a simple force balance [8]:

$$\tau = \frac{\sigma_f d}{2l_c} \quad (1)$$

where d is the fiber diameter, σ_f is the fiber failure strength.

An alternative technique to measure the interfacial properties is the micro-indentation test [9-10]. In contrast to the single fiber fragmentation test, the micro-indentation test is conducted on real composites and therefore has the advantage of reflecting actual processing conditions. A compressive force is applied to a individually selected fibers in a polished cross-section of the composite to produce debonding. The interfacial shear strength is then derived from the debond load. However, the interfacial strength from the microindentation test is also a derived rather than a directly measured quantity. In principle, the interfacial shear strength is calculated through the use of the experimental curve-fit of the $\sigma_{deb}-T_m/d$ curve (where σ_{deb} is the debond load, T_m is the distance from the indented fiber to the nearest neighbor fiber and d is the diameter of the indented fiber) of a model composite and the application of a linear finite element analysis [9]. This data reduction scheme results in an expression for the interfacial shear strength [11]

$$\tau/\sigma_{deb} = 0.8757 (G_m/E_f)^{0.5} - 0.01863 \times \log(d/T_m) - 0.026496 \quad (2)$$

where G_m and E_f are the matrix shear and fiber axial moduli, respectively. This equation is embedded in the experimental apparatus and is indiscriminately used for glass and carbon fiber composites. A closed form shear lag equation is also used to derive the interfacial shear strength [9]:

$$\tau/\sigma_{deb} = 0.5 \times (G_m/E_f)^{0.5} (d/T_m)^{0.5} \quad (3)$$

Because the single fiber fragmentation and microindentation tests differ substantially in the principle of their operation, it is expected that the interfacial shear strengths obtained from these two methods will show certain variation. Indeed it has been reported so in the literature. However, the measured interfacial shear strengths sometimes differ as large as 100%!

The purpose of this research is to look into the mechanics behind these two tests in more detail and provide some insight to these two experimental techniques. Specimens were prepared with graphite fibers coated with preceramic silicon oxycarbide and heat treated at different temperatures. Single fiber fragmentation and microindentation tests were performed to measure the interfacial shear strengths for the coated and heat treated fibers at various temperatures. Interfacial shear strengths derived from these two tests were compared. Nonlinear finite element analyses were applied to study the mechanics of these two tests. The discrepancy between the test results was discussed based on the test mechanics.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

A layer of the processable inorganic polymer precursor coatings were applied to graphite fibers by dip coating tows of fibers into hexane solutions of the silsesquioxane terpolymer $-\text{[MeHSiO]}_{0.1}\text{[MeSi(OnPr)O]}_{0.2}\text{[MeSi(O)}_{1.5}\text{]}_{0.7}-$. The silsesquioxane coatings typically are 0.1 μm thick. The coatings are then pretreated by heating in N_2 to selected temperatures (200°C increments to 1000°C). Auger electron spectroscopy (AES) and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) were used to quantify the structural and compositional changes that occur at different heat treatment temperatures. It was found that the amorphous polymeric coatings converted to amorphous silicon oxycarbide coatings on heating to temperatures above 600°C. Single fiber fragmentation and microindentation tests were then applied to characterize the adhesion and fracture behavior of the coatings with different degree of pyrolysis.

The single fiber fragmentation specimens were fabricated by encapsulating the coated and heat treated fibers into Epon 828 epoxy resin cured with 14.5 wt.% metaphenylene diamine (mPDA). For the microindentation test, several fibers were embedded in the Epon 828 epoxy matrix and then cut into small pieces which were then embedded in a metallographic specimen mount with the fibers normal to a specimen surface. The details of specimen preparation, test procedures and experimental apparatus for microindentation test can be found in reference 9.

FINITE ELEMENT MODELS

SINGLE FIBER FRAGMENTATION

A schematic diagram of the single fiber fragmentation finite element model is shown in Fig. 1, where the single fiber coupon is modeled as a combination of three concentric cylinders representing the fiber, interphase, and matrix. The aspect ratio (fiber length/fiber diameter) for the fragment analyzed is 126.5, which is more than twice the critical length for graphite epoxy composites. The outer matrix diameter of the model is 10.8 times the fiber diameter. The fiber diameter and interphase thickness are 8 and 0.16 microns, respectively. Along the symmetric and axisymmetric (fiber center line) axes, roller constraints are applied which restrain the normal displacement but allow for the shear deformation for the nodal points at these two boundaries. Immediately after the fiber breaks, the fiber will recoil and the matrix will stretch further due to the relaxation of the constraints imposed by the fiber. Thus a gap will be formed between the fragments and will extend with increasing applied strain. A gap length of 2 microns is used in this model. The outer cylindrical surface is a free boundary and a uniform displacement is applied at the upper edge as shown in Fig. 1. Three layers of elements are used for the interphase. A total of 3927 nodes and 3409 axisymmetric four-node elements are used for the model. Elements are refined at regions near the fiber breaks. A displacement $\delta=8$ microns is applied to the matrix cross section to induce approximately the fiber failure stress.

Fig. 1. Finite element models for single fiber fragmentation and microindentation tests.

MICROINDENTATION

The finite element model of the microindentation specimen is similar to that of the single fiber fragmentation specimen. It is a axisymmetric four-phase model with a fiber volume fraction $V_f=25\%$, which reflects the fiber selection criteria required by the experimental set-up. The criteria for the selection of the fiber to be indented is that at least two neighbor fibers are at or within half of a diameter away from the selected fiber. A schematic diagram of the microindentation model is also shown in Fig. 1. The indenter is modeled as a rigid half sphere.

The load is applied to the top surface of the indenter. The downward displacement of the indenter is monitored such that the fiber won't be crushed. Because the sample is embedded in a metallographic specimen, an elastic/plastic foundation is modeled to sit beneath the sample.

THE MATERIAL BEHAVIOR

AS4 fiber, which is transversely isotropic and linearly elastic with $E_1=241\text{GPa}$, $E_2=21\text{GPa}$, $G_{12}=28\text{GPa}$, $G_{23}=8.3\text{GPa}$ and $\nu_{12}=0.25$, is used. The matrix is Epon 828 epoxy resin with 14.5 wt.% mPDA. The interphase is assumed to be a layer of more brittle material, such as Epon 828 epoxy resin with 7.5 wt.% mPDA [12]. The material response curves for Epon 828 with 14.5 wt.% mPDA (the matrix) and Epon 828 with 7.5 wt.% mPDA (the interphase) are shown in Fig. 2 where it can be seen that the interphase is linearly elastic ($\nu=0.3$) while the matrix ($\nu=0.35$) is nonlinearly elasto-plastic. The matrix is assumed to behave perfectly plastic after 6% strain in the finite element analysis. In the fragmentation analysis, the fragment is assumed to be created at 1% matrix strains. For microindentation test, the composite properties are calculated using the rule of mixtures.

Fig. 2. Stress-strain curve of the constituent materials.

One major goal of the finite element analyses is to evaluate the effect of coating property change as a result of heat treatment at different temperatures. Stress fields for specimens with interphase properties $E_i/E_f=0.009$, 0.0185, 0.092, and 0.369 in both models are evaluated, where E_i and E_f are the interphase and fiber axial moduli, respectively.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

EXPERIMENTS

As reported in reference 2, the copolymer is stable to 200°C; however, on heating to 400°C it loses the starting monomer units $-\text{[MeHSiO]}-$ and transforms to a polymer consisting solely of $-\text{[MeSi(O)}_{1.5}\text{]}_x-$ or "T" monomer units. At 600°C this "T" monomer is relatively stable but a slight redistribution of the T groups to form $-\text{[(CH}_2\text{)}_2\text{SiO]}_{0.2}\text{[SiO}_2\text{]}_{0.3}\text{[MeSi(O)}_{1.5}\text{]}_{0.5}$ is noted. At 800°C, redistribution is more pronounced giving a product with a composition of $-\text{[(CH}_2\text{)}_2\text{SiO]}_{0.2}\text{[SiO}_2\text{]}_{0.3}\text{[MeSi(O)}_{1.5}\text{]}_{0.5}$. In this instance, the Si-C bonds are cleaved and free carbon is formed. The process is much more extensive at 1000°C. In a word, the conversion from the preceramic inorganic polymer has been completed at temperatures above 600°C. At 1000°C, SiO_2 and free C are formed. The coatings increase the fiber oxidation resistance by 75-100°C relative to uncoated fibers.

To investigate how the coatings of various heat treatment affect the fiber-matrix adhesion under processing conditions, the single fiber fragmentation and microindentation tests are performed. The interfacial shear strengths derived from fragmentation and microindentation tests using Eqns (1) & (2) are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Interfacial shear strength (IFSS) derived from single fiber fragmentation (SFFT) and microindentation tests (MIT)

		200°C	400°C	600°C	800°C	1000°C
SFFT	l_c/d	130±7	118±15	107±10	53±4	59±6
	IFSS (MPa)	8.27±0.41	9.58±1.58	10.34±0.83	23.86±2.0	19.10±1.34
MIT	IFSS (MPa)	6.87±0.66	6.83±0.72	6.57±0.63	7.09±0.70	10.8±1.06

The interfacial shear strength values for coated fibers treated at and below 600°C as derived from microindentation test are virtually the same. However, the interfacial shear strength values as derived from fragmentation test increases 25% as the temperature increases from 200°C to 600°C. At 800°C, the interfacial shear strength derived from fragmentation test increases 188% from the 200°C value while the increase is only 3.2% for the microindentation test. At 1000°C, the interfacial shear strength decreases 20% from the 800°C value for the fragmentation test but for the microindentation test it increases about 52%. Thus the temperature at which the IFSS increases for these two tests is not the same and the rate of increase is also significantly different. Because the conversion of the coating from preceramic polymer to ceramic occurs after 600°C, it is expected that the interfacial shear strengths won't be the same for coatings treated below and above 600°C. However, the discrepancy in the interfacial shear strength values for fragmentation and microindentation tests, especially at high temperatures, suggests that these two tests probably are not measuring the same material property. The discrepancy will be elaborated in terms of the test mechanics in the following section.

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

Single Fiber Fragmentation Test

For the single fiber fragmentation test, interface debonding occurs immediately following fiber fractures due to the stress singularity at the free edges [13]. Interface debonding is evidenced by the photoelastic stress patterns [3] for coatings treated at all temperatures. Thus at the end of the test each fiber segment contains debonded and well bonded regions. Thus the perfect-bond assumption in arriving at Eqn (1) is violated. Though polymer matrix is not perfectly plastic, if the fiber and the matrix are perfectly bonded, Eqn (1), in fact, can still be used as an equation for *relative* interfacial shear strength. However, when debonding occurs, Eqn (1) should be treated as an index for interfacial toughness rather than interfacial shear strength. Since higher resistance to debond propagation can be translated to higher stress transfer efficiency; the critical length l_c then can be treated as an index for interfacial fracture toughness. If the single fiber fragmentation test is measuring the interfacial debonding resistance rather than the interfacial shear strength, it is not surprising that there is significant discrepancy in the derived interfacial shear strengths between the fragmentation and microindentation tests, Table 1.

It has been shown in the literature [14-16] that the interfacial toughness is highly dependent on the modulus ratio of the neighboring materials. Sawyer and Anderson [14] used truncated Williams power series stress function to calculate the interfacial stress intensity factors of a two-phase plate model of a single continuous reinforcing element in a matrix material broken at regular intervals with debonding near the fractured ends. It was shown that when the matrix/fiber modulus ratio increases from 0.05 to 0.5, the interfacial stress intensity factor may decrease as much as 50%. In the heat treated coating case, the coating is converted from preceramic polymer into ceramic at temperatures above 600°C thus the coating becomes more brittle and the modulus is higher. According to Sawyer and Anderson, the stress intensity factors for the 800°C and 1000°C coated fibers would be lower due to the increase of coating/fiber modulus ratio; thus the driving force for debond propagation is smaller. Sawyer and Anderson also showed that as debond grows, the interfacial stress intensity factor decreases and at a certain point the interfacial cracks would be self arresting. Similar arguments were presented by Lin and Mar [15] and Rice and Sih [16]. The finite element solution of Lin and

Mar for the stress intensity factor k_2 for a crack along the bimaterial interface in a square panel under biaxial stresses agrees very well with the exact solution of Rice and Sih. Both solutions indicated that while the mode I stress intensity factor k_1 is not sensitive to the material modulus ratio, the mode II stress intensity factor k_2 decreases about 50% when the modulus ratio increases from 1/1000 to 1/3. Though the models used by Sawyer and Anderson, Lin and Mar, Rice and Sih were two-dimensional plate analyses, their results indicated qualitatively that the bimaterial modulus ratio has a significant effect on the debond/crack propagation. The calculation of the stress intensity factor, or more precisely the strain energy release rate, for various coating-fiber modulus ratio in the current finite element model is more complicated and is not provided here because the elastic strain energy has to be isolated from the plastic and frictional dissipation energy. This phase of work will be pursued by the authors in the future. Nevertheless, results from this finite element stress analysis of the fragmentation test showed that the interfacial shear stress induced as a result of a fiber break is not sensitive to the material modulus ratio E_i/E_f . As shown in Fig. 3a, the interfacial shear stress reaches approximately the same plateau except that the shear plateau for $E_i/E_f=0.369$ shows certain oscillations. The fiber ineffective lengths are therefore approximately the same for all E_i/E_f . In addition, due to matrix plasticity, the interfacial shear stress would not increase monotonically with higher applied strains. Thus the abrupt change in the experimentally measured l_c/d must be driven by other factor, such as the strain energy release rate, rather than the interfacial shear stress.

In summary, it is evident that the increase of coating properties at temperatures above 600°C affects the interfacial toughness and reduce the strain energy release rate upon crack growth; therefore the debond length is shorter, which in turn results in shorter l_c . However, the decrease in l_c length cannot be interpreted as the increase in interfacial shear strength.

Fig. 3. Interfacial shear stress distributions for various E_i/E_f ratio for (a) single fiber fragmentation, (b) microindentation tests for debond load $F=4.7$ grams.

Microindentation Test

Unlike the fragmentation test, matrix plasticity does not play an important role (if any) in the measurement of interfacial shear strength for microindentation test. Because the compressive load is applied to the fiber center, debonding usually occur before matrix yield. The load point is away from the bimaterial free edge thus stress singularity is not likely. However, the matrix deformation is still nonlinear rather than linear. As shown in Fig. 3b, the interfacial shear stress for various E_i/E_f ratio does not reach a shear plateau as was the case for the single fiber fragmentation test. The maximum shear stress is about three quarters of the fiber diameter away from the free edge. Thus the initiation of debonding occurs at regions very close to the free edge if there is no defect at the free edge.

The FEM results showed that as the interphase or coating modulus increases, the interfacial shear stress increases. As the coating/fiber modulus ratio increases from 0.009 to 0.369, the interfacial shear stress increases 20.5%, Table 2. The experimental results showed that the interfacial shear strength derived from Eqn (2) for fiber coating treated at 1000°C is about 57% higher than that of fiber coating treated at and below 600°C. The increase of the experimentally measured interfacial shear strength from 800°C to 1000°C is believed to be a result of higher interphase strength and better adhesion between fiber and coating as the coating is converted from preceramic polymer to ceramic. Strictly speaking, interfacial failure could be caused by bonding failure between the fiber and the coating and the failure of the coating itself. Usually it

is difficult to distinguish between these two failure modes, especially when the interphase is very thin. For weak bonding, bonding failure occurs before interphase failure and the maximum interphase shear stress at the time of debonding can be treated as the interfacial shear strength. For very strong fiber-coating bonding, coating or interphase failure occurs before bonding failure. Still, coating shear failure will initiate at the interface at the 45° maximum stress direction. However, once the crack is initiated the crack propagation and the local stress fields should be analyzed by fracture mechanics rather than stress analysis. In addition to possible shear failure of the coating, coating compressive fracture might occur for strong fiber-coating bonding. The fracture of the coating will induce stress concentration and promote debonding at the interface. Nonetheless, the microindentation test only measures the load at debonding thus the finite element stress analysis is adequate to predict the interfacial shear strength. Either it is a bonding failure or a coating failure, the measured failure strength is directly related to the coating properties. The deficiency in the finite element analysis is that the bonding condition cannot be modeled because the bonding strength is not known *a priori*. However, the important issue here is that the rate of interfacial shear strength increase is predictable from the finite element stress analysis. The load measured is for debond initiation rather than propagation; thus the microindentation test is more appropriate for interfacial shear strength measurement.

Table 2. Interfacial shear stresses for various E_j/E_f ratio for carbon fiber composite at a debond load $F=4.7$ grams from microindentation FEM.

modulus ratio	$E_j/E_f=0.009$	$E_j/E_f=0.0185$	$E_j/E_f=0.092$	$E_j/E_f=0.369$
IFSS (MPa)	32.01	32.85	34.75	38.56

One of the objectives in this finite element analysis of microindentation test is to compare the results of the current non-linear model with those from Eqn (2) and shear lag analysis, Eqn (3). As shown in Table 3, the interfacial shear stresses obtained from Eqns (2) & (3) at an applied debond load $F=4.7$ grams are much higher than that obtained from the nonlinear finite element analysis. One of the reasons is that Eqns (1) & (2) assume linear matrix properties which in turn produce higher interfacial shear stress. It could be also caused by the non-exact nature of curve-fitting technique. Further study is needed to evaluate the validity of Eqn (2). Note that while T_m is defined as the distance from the indented fiber to the nearest neighbor fiber in the experiment, it is defined as the matrix thickness in the three phase axisymmetric linear FEM [9]. The average T_m in the neighborhood of the indented fiber from experiment is actually much higher than the T_m of the indented fiber to the nearest fiber. Thus the interfacial shear strength derived from the linear finite element analysis will be much higher than the experimental value (see Fig. 11 of reference 9). In summary, the interfacial shear stress obtained from Eqn (2) is overestimated. The accuracy of the derived interfacial shear strength depends on how nonlinear the matrix behavior is and how far away the T_m used in Eqn (2) is from the average T_m . However, the microindentation test does provide a relative interfacial shear strength value.

Table 3. Interfacial shear strength values for AS4/Epon 828 at debond load $F=4.7$ grams and $T_m=4\mu\text{m}$.

curve-fitting & linear FEM	shear lag	nonlinear FEM
54.71	43.90	32.85

CONCLUSIONS

The interfacial shear strengths obtained from the single fiber fragmentation and the microindentation tests are found to be inconsistent for preceramic fiber coatings treated at various temperatures. The inconsistency is due to different mechanics for these two tests. While the microindentation test can be regarded as the interfacial shear strength test, the single fiber fragmentation test is more like an interfacial toughness test. Despite the difference, both tests provide important information for interface optimization and the tailoring of composite properties.

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